

Non-Periodic Star Mapper Patterns

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(The following is a summary and extension of the note, "Optimization of Non-Periodic Star Mapper Patterns", 1982 March 3.)

SLIT AMBIGUITY

The "slit ambiguity" problem is almost completely eliminated with a simple rearrangement of the star mapper slits into a "non-periodic" pattern, and by using a suitably matched numerical filter. A sidelobe suppression factor (SSF) exceeding 30 is readily achieved, corresponding to 3.7 magnitudes.

FILTER FUNCTION

Fig. 1 shows how the matched numerical filter works for a slit pattern with four slits. The photometric counts (n_k) are convolved, first with a long but sparse filter (F), then with a short and dense filter (f). The result, $f * F * n_k$, is an almost clean peak with height proportional to the star's intensity. Note that the long filter is balanced ($\sum_k F_k = 0$), so the filter output is not affected by a constant background count level. $SSF = 36$.

FILTER IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 2 shows how the four-slits filter can be implemented in software or hardware. Only 22 additions and 7 multiplications (4 of which by powers of 2) are required per photometric sample. The filter is thus computationally both simple and efficient, which is important both for the on-board processing and for the TYCHO reductions.

Fig. 3 shows an alternative slit pattern and filter using 8 slits. This has a slightly smaller $SSF = 30.7$, and requires more arithmetic operations per sample.

POSITIONAL ACCURACY

It is not always true that more slits give higher accuracy. If for instance photon noise from the sky background (which is proportional to N , the number of slits) is the dominating noise source, then the mean error *per slit* goes as $\sqrt{N}$ and the average for N slits will have a mean error *independent* of N .

Therefore it is interesting to compare the mean errors for the two patterns mentioned above, having 4 and 8 slits respectively. This is shown in Table 1, where the slit dimensions etc are as given in Fig. 4.

It is found that, for faint stars ($B \geq 10$) and/or enhanced sky brightness ($B_{\text{sky}} < 22.5 \text{ arcsec}^{-2}$), the four-slit pattern may in fact be better than the eight slits.

VERTICAL AND INCLINED SLITS

Two possible arrangements are proposed for discussion, Fig. 4 and 5. Each thick line here represents a group of four or eight slits.

In Fig. 4 the transits across the inclined groups are distinguished from "vertical" transits by coincidence detection, using the known time difference between the parallel groups.

In Fig. 5 the ambiguity between differently inclined groups is entirely removed by having only one group per star mapper.

B _{star}	B _{sky}	4 slits/group			8 slits/group		
		σ_v	σ_i	σ_ζ	σ_v	σ_i	σ_ζ
9	22.5	".05	".05	".07	".04	".04	".06
10	22.5	.10	.09	.13	.09	.09	.13
11	22.5	.21	.20	.29	.22	.20	.30
9	20.0	".11	".10	".15	".10	".09	".14
10	20.0	.21	.20	.29	.25	.23	.34
11	20.0	.52	.48	.71	.61	.57	.84

TABLE 1. Positional accuracy versus stellar magnitude (B_{star}) for normal sky brightness (B_{sky} = 22.5 per arcsec²) and 10x normal (B_{sky} = 20.0).

σ_v = mean error for a transit across the vertical group of 4 or 8 slits
 σ_i = mean error for a transit across two inclined groups
 $\sigma_\zeta = \sqrt{(\sigma_v^2 + \sigma_i^2)}$ mean error of the determination of vertical coordinate (ζ) from one star mapper transit.

Main assumptions:

- Diffraction limited optics $\times 0.8$ in MTF; semi-circular 0.32 m ϕ , $\epsilon = 0.5$
- Stellar count rate = 4320 Hz for B = 10, B-V = 0.5 with grid removed
- Dark count rate = 300 Hz
- Sampling frequency = 600 Hz
- Slit dimensions (Fig. 4 and 5):
 - vertical slits: 40' $\times$ 0".4
 - inclined slits: 20' $\times$ 0".8 (measured along scan)
 - total area = 11520 arcsec² for 4 slits/group;
 = 23040 arcsec² for 8 slits/group

FIGURE 2a. Slit pattern (G_i), filter coefficients (g_i) and their convolution (Γ_i).

FIG 2b. Realization of $S = 83$ filter ($N = 4$, $N/\epsilon = 36.0$). 22 additions and 7 multiplications per sample.

FIG. 3a.

FIG. 3b. Realization of $S = 2479$ filter ($N = 8$, $N/\epsilon = 30\frac{2}{3}$). 26 additions and 13 multiplications per sample.

← Kovalentsev's proposal